

Belief Space Planning for Robust Humanoid Locomotion

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Abstract: We have implemented a BSP (Belief Space Planning) controller inspired by human walking behaviour's neurophysiological mechanisms on the PAL Robotics REEM-C humanoid robot. BSP controllers assuming maximum likelihood have been previously successfully utilized by our group for various similar demanding applications. The posture and locomotion performance of the REEM-C robot with BSP controllers has been experimentally tested and validated in the Eurobench @IIT humanoid testing facility by means of the benchmarking framework and software already developed in Eurobench. The main purpose of the work reported here is to assess if and how the application of a BSP controller is viable and useful in the humanoid robotics domain. The BSP walking controller has shown remarkably good performance in tracking tasks. However, it has not performed well on slopes in simulation. A new more advanced approach aiming to cope with slopes and unstable terrain is under development.

Keywords: Belief Space Planning, Target chasing, Biped Walking, Human locomotion.

1. MOTIVATION

In the work reported here we have tested in the context of Humanoid Robotics a Belief Space Planning (BSP) methodology that we have largely tested in the latest years in a variety of demanding experimental settings in the field and in simulation. The BSP plans the walking towards a colored blob target and keeps the sagittal (longitudinal) plane of the head horizontal. The BSP planner sends inputs and receive data from the PAL Walking controller of REEM-C; it has proven very robust and effective in managing uncertainties and unexpected situations in many different experimental settings. It was natural for us to test it on a Humanoid Robot (PAL Robotics REEM-C). To that purpose we have implemented a planning strategy for locomotion that is inspired by what is known to be the planning motion strategy in humans. Alain Berthoz and his collaborators have shown in Pozzo et al. (1995) that in humans the balancing during locomotion is obtained by keeping horizontal the sagittal plane of the head: the gaze is fixed on the target with the help of the vestibular system and the motion is 'top-down' planned. Actually, it has been shown that human subjects can walk also without vision help by simulating the gaze through the proprioceptive feedback received by the vestibular system. We planned to implement a simplified version of this mechanism by relaying on vision and correcting the vision signal by fusion with the signals coming from available REEM-C's IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit), Xsens MTI-30-AHRS, mounted on the head, mimicking vestibular reflex. In our experiments, the BSP plans a trajectory for the robot

from its current position to the goal, while reducing the uncertainty related to the measures and the motion itself; such trajectory is approximated into segments exploiting Direct Transcription technique, to optimize it. A useful basic reference is provided by Betts (2010). Further, a Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) is employed to find control actions that suitably move the robot from one segment to the subsequent one in the planned trajectory, thus assuring the robot convergence towards its goal. We send commands to REEM-C through the PAL Walking controller, imposing the optimal actions at the beginning of each planning segment, as obtained by the direct transcription defined above. This hybrid approach, aiming to blend the motion objectives with those related to the reduction of the uncertainties on the measures, seems very suitable to a walking task on an inclined or soft slope where the uncertainties in the measurements and perception can be relevant. The work was developed within the HumaBeliefs sub-project of the H2020 Eurobench EU project. The results are potentially interesting both from a scientific standpoint (for humanoid research and human neurophysiology understanding) and to make easier practical applications of humanoids. The primary objective of our work is to check if the BSP approach performs well also on complex robot HW/SW platforms such as humanoid robots. Vision guided locomotion is not new in humanoid robotics (see: Stasse et al. (2007); Michel et al. (2007); Garcia et al. (2014)). In comparison, for example, to Michel et al. (2007) it does not directly rely on a full fledged realtime 3D tracking, while with respect to Stasse et al. (2007); Garcia et al. (2014) it does not use, in

this early prototypical implementation, specially designed Vision-guided motion primitives to implement the reactive walking behavior of the robot. Our work is somehow in line with Cupec et al. (2004), although our approach to computer vision is much simpler, and Seara and Schmidt (2004), although in our case Kalman filters are embedded into the BSP algorithm. The novelty of this work from a humanoid robotics perspective is twofold: 1) we tested for the first time ever (to our knowledge) a BSP locomotion planner on a humanoid robot; 2) we performed our experiment in a measurable and reproducible way, making our experimental data available on the Eurobench platform. This is important, as basic our approach could seem - in a context where the data substantiating the claims are not usually shared. We also give more extensive practical and technical details than usual about our experiments with the purpose of easing our experiments reproducibility w.r.t. to the work cited above about vision guided locomotion in humanoids. The expected benefits of the BSP w.r.t. PID with observers approaches or Model Predictive Control schemes lie in its remarkable robustness, extensively tested by the authors on a very hard to control platform like the H2Arm Bonsignorio and Zereik (2021), and confirmed by the less extensive and preliminary but in a controlled and supervised experiments reported here.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOLS

We have initially identified the following scenarios, within the Eurobench envisioned ones:

- (1) Walking on flat ground
- (2) Tracking of a moving target
- (3) Ascending/Descending slopes
- (4) Walking on laterally inclined surfaces
- (5) Walking over irregular terrains
- (6) Walking over soft terrains

Scenarios (1), (2) and (3) have been extensively tested in simulation. Number (1) and (2) have been successfully tested in the real world in the Eurobench @IIT testing facility. Since the simulation performance of REEM-C in scenario (3) was poor, the development of a more advanced approach (that will be discussed below) has been triggered. Should this approach be successful, we will test it also on Scenarios (4), (5) and (6). We started from scenarios (1) and (2) listed above, extensively tested in simulation and in the real world at the Eurobench @IIT Humanoid Testing facility at the IIT laboratories located in Genoa, Italy, and progressing then to the more difficult ones. For every scenario addressed in the real world experiments, we have recorded the full rosbags of the experimental runs. From the rosbag file, relevant metrics can be extracted: success rate on a given task, average time and max time to execute the task when successful, percentage of correctly executed tests, average time to execute the task, other metrics that we will find relevant during the test campaigns. In the future we plan similar and more demanding tests on the still not coped with scenarios.

3. BELIEF SPACE PLANNING

We have exploited Belief Space Planning, assuming maximum observation likelihood, in many different activities of

our Joint Heron-CNR Lab (<http://heron-at-cnr.org>) since several years with excellent results. Such methods have already been analyzed in simulation Platt et al. (2010); Bonsignorio (2011) and have shown promising results for very different kinds of demanding applications. In our past work with Belief Space planning, we applied the methodology to leader-follower navigation underwater Zereik et al. (2014), swarm behaviour implementation Bonsignorio et al. (2019); Berman et al. (2020) and reaching movements during manipulation Bonsignorio and Zereik (2021). A belief space trajectory for the robot moves it from its current relative position, expressed as a distance to a goal position, while reducing the covariance of the error. Both the initial and the goal positions are represented by Gaussian Probability Density Functions (PDFs), whose mean represents the estimated position in the state space. An interesting characteristic of the BSP is that it drives the system to the desired position in the state space, simultaneously reducing the uncertainty, expressed by the covariance component of the Gaussian distributions. We approximate the planning trajectories by a series of segments in the belief space, optimized by direct transcription, to which we apply a Linear Quadratic Regulator (LQR) to move from one extreme of a segment to the beginning of the following one. The actions in the belief space weigh the objective to reduce and keep the relative distance from the target, retaining the head aligned on the sagittal plane, with the objective of reducing the uncertainty on the measures. Following the approach initially proposed by Platt et al. (2010), and already considered in Zereik et al. (2015) and tested in various context over the years, we a-priori plan a trajectory in the belief space by direct transcription method and then apply LQR method to stabilize the trajectory taking into account the upgrading measurements gathered by the system. The process is iterated until the desired position with lower covariance is reached. We model the observation $z_t \in Z$ on the blob position w.r.t. the robot as a non linear stochastic function of the d-dimensional state vector $x_t \in X$

$$z_t = g(x_t) + \xi \quad (1)$$

where g is a deterministic function of the measurement and ξ is a zero mean Gaussian noise with covariance W_t dependent on the state of the system. Two consecutive time dependent states are linked by a control action u_t

$$x_{t+1} = f(x_t, u_t) \quad (2)$$

where f and g are differentiable functions of x_t and u_t . The system model can be further simplified by assuming the belief state described by a Gaussian PDF $P(x)$

$$\Sigma_t : P(x) = \mathcal{N}(x/m_t, \Sigma_t) \quad (3)$$

and by linearization of the belief space dynamic leading to

$$x_{t+1} = A_t(x_t - m_t) + f(m_t, u_t) \quad (4)$$

$$z_t = C_t(x_t - m_t) + g(f(m_t, u_t)) + \xi \quad (5)$$

where m_t is the mean of the belief state and A_t and C_t are the Jacobian matrices $A_t = \frac{\delta f}{\delta x}(m_t, u_t)$, $C_t = \frac{\delta g}{\delta x}(m_t)$. In this hypothesis it is possible to derive a series of states and of actions finding local minima of the cost function J by a standard SQP (Sequential Quadratic Programming) algorithm

$$J(b_{\tau:T}, u_{\tau:T}) = \sum_{i=1}^k w_i (\hat{n}_i^T \Sigma_i \hat{n}_i)^2 + \sum_{t=\tau}^{T-1} \tilde{m}_t^T Q \hat{m}_t + \tilde{u}_t^T R \tilde{u}_t \quad (6)$$

Fig. 1. The humanoid robot REEM-C.

where $b_{\tau:T}$ is the subset of the state space, $u_{\tau:T}$ are the corresponding actions for a given state space trajectory, Q and R are weight matrices, the n_i are the versors of belief space along which the optimization is performed. Finally, Σ_T is the covariance matrix at the end of the segment, and m_i^T the value of the mean of the Gaussian of the measures.

4. REEM-C HUMANOID ROBOT

REEM-C is a commercial humanoid robot produced by PAL Robotics, shown in Figure 1.

REEM-C is 165 cm tall, has 44 degrees of freedom, is equipped with two i7 computers, force/torque and range finders on each feet, a stereo camera, 4 microphones, and other sensors. It is one of the more reliable humanoid platforms available. Optionally, a depth camera can also be attached to the head. There is a comparatively large collection of developed software for walking, grasping, navigation and human-robot interaction. REEM-C runs on ROS internally, and uses state-of-the-art ros control and OROCOS PAL Robotics. REEM-C has a rich documentation PAL-Robotics (2019) to which we will contribute with the outputs of our project. We added a novel planner to the REEM-C available software with the necessary interfaces.

5. EXPERIMENTS

5.1 Eurobench @IIT Testing Facility

We performed experiments on REEM-C at the IIT Testing Facility in Genoa, Italy. The Eurobench @IIT Testing facility is dedicated to performing benchmarks for humanoid locomotion. The workspace for the benchmarking facility consists of an equipped indoor area and a storage area. The indoor space is about $100 m^2$. The facility provides a testing track with curved and straight path similar to a small size running circuit. The width of the track is approximately $1.5 m$ which is sufficiently large to place the portable test benches like door, stairs, other kind of obstacles and disturbance devices. A large gantry system allows the safe execution of experiments, allowing to carry the humanoid (REEM-C in our case) in the testing track and to hold them in case of failures of the locomotion system, preventing falls that could damage the robots.

Proper safety procedures have been implemented for the researchers and other operators.

The facility includes cameras at fixed locations to enable continuous recording of the events in the benchmarking area. The testing facility also provides a large treadmill, disturbing equipment, slopes and various devices and materials to simulate slopes. A number of linux based control workstations connected to the cameras and other sensing and testing equipment are organized in a local VPN allowing to fine grain the desired level of disclosure of the data collected through the experiments.

5.2 Experimental Setup

We asked REEM-C to follow a red blob (a simple circle) while walking, centering it in its camera’s image plane and always keeping a pre-defined distance from it. The task was continuously active: in case the red blob move in the environment after REEM-C centered it, the high-level controller would send again suitable reference to the robot in such a way to keep tracking the target. In order to prove the effectiveness of our proposed approach, we employed the standard walking controller provided by PAL Robotics, and developed our high-level controllers on top of it.

The system architecture we employed is made up of different components: i) standard walking controller; ii) vision-based blob recognition and pose estimation; iii) BSP high-level controller. The whole REEM-C architecture exploits the Robot Operating System (ROS) Koubâa et al. (2017), Melodic version, and is based on Linux Ubuntu 18.04. The three modules communicate through standard ROS topics: the vision-based recognition algorithm publishes a `PoseStamped` variable containing the red blob estimated position. Such topic is read by the BSP controller and exploited to compute the robot residual error with respect to the desired final position. The BSP high-level approach plans the robot motion according to this residual error and publishes, at each sample time, a velocity reference in a `Twist` message for REEM-C walking controller; this last drives the robot to fulfil the requested velocity.

The scheme in Figure 2 summarizes the overall architecture and shows inter-node communication during a walking simulation exploiting Gazebo Koenig and Howard (2004). The feature detector node acquires, at each sample time, the image from the robot camera, processes it with simple artificial vision algorithms and publishes the estimated blob position. Such position is exploited by the BSP planner to provide the motion needed to compensate the residual task error and reach the target.

Details on each single node are provided in the following.

5.3 Vision-based blob recognition node

The vision-based blob recognition module is in charge of detecting the red blob to be followed in the environment and to estimate its position in the 3D space. The algorithm itself is very simple and not very accurate; in fact the focus of our research work was on the BSP-based motion planning and on the walking task. Even if improvements in the robot sensing could be foreseen, this simple vision algorithm allowed to obtain good results in the task of detecting, tracking and following (keeping a predefined

Fig. 2. Visualization of the overall architecture through the utility `rqt_graph`. Our nodes are highlighted in green and orange, and their topics interacting with the other system nodes are depicted in blue.

distance) the object of interest. This node is implemented in Python and exploits the OpenCV 3.2 library. The algorithm reads the camera image from the ROS topic `/camera/color/image_raw/compressed` (published by either the Gazebo simulator or the real REEM-C robot) as a `CompressedImage` BGR data structure and convert it in the HSV color space Sural et al. (2002) to easily retrieve all the red pixels through suitable image masking and filtering. This process outputs a new image containing only the pixels that survived the thresholding and were labeled as “red”; a procedure to find contours is therefore applied to such image to retrieve all the objects present in the scene. The contours are sorted and the biggest one, in terms of underlying area, is considered the object to be tracked; its minimum enclosing circle, center and radius are computed. Moreover, an image mask is set/updated and applied to subsequent camera frames, augmenting by 5% the size of the tracking area, in order to take into account the robot motion occurring between adjacent frames. Note that the choice of selecting the biggest red blob as object to be tracked is not much robust: in case a different bigger red object is present in the scene the robot would track that one, instead of the real target. However, since the vision algorithm was beyond the scope of our system, the assumption to just have one red object in view was made to simplify the perception; obviously, the system could become more robust if a more complex recognition system is implemented, e.g. exploiting shape matching or other object recognition techniques. Finally, the blob 3D position in space is computed exploiting knowledge of the real object size and of the camera intrinsic parameters, through the known relation: $X = \frac{z}{f}(C - p)$, where X represents the x , y coordinates in the 3D space, z is the the third space coordinate along the camera optical axis, f is the camera focal length, C and p are the center of the blob minimum enclosing circle retrieved in the image and the camera principal point, respectively, according to the standard pinhole camera model. Finally, the reconstructed blob position is published in the topic `/camera/color/redBlobPose` for the BSP planner to exploit it.

5.4 BSP motion planner node

The BSP planner reads the red blob estimated position from the topic `/camera/color/redBlobPose` as a `PoseStamped` ROS struct, and computes the residual task error e_t exploiting the knowledge of the vector representing

the desired final position of the blob w.r.t. the robot camera. From e_t a motion plan is created, in terms of action-state tuples (\bar{u}_j, \bar{m}_j) , able to drive the robot to the target. For each planned motion, a LQR computes the optimal control actions u_t , relying also on the measurements z_t published by the feature detector node, and evolves the system state m_t through a standard Extended Kalman Filter. Whenever the planned motion diverges too much from the target, a replanning action occurs, assuring convergence towards the goal. Suitable references are sent to the robot control system, specifically a `Twist` velocity is sent to the walking controller through the ROS topic `/walking_controller/cmd_vel`, a velocity command for the REEM-C Center of Gravity (COG). Algorithm 1 summarizes all the BSP steps.

Input : m_0, m_{goal}

Output: $u_{1:s}$

```

1 initBSP ()
2 while  $\|e_t\| > thr_2$  do
3    $(\bar{u}_{1:s}, \bar{m}_{1:s}) \leftarrow \text{CreateMotionPlan}(m_t, m_{goal})$ 
4   for  $i = iCnt$  to  $s$  do
5      $u_t \leftarrow \text{LQR}(\bar{u}_t, \bar{m}_t, m_t)$ 
6      $z_t \leftarrow \text{ReadBlob3Dposition}()$ 
7      $e_t \leftarrow m_{goal} - z_t + \xi$ 
8      $m_{t+1} \leftarrow \text{EKF}(m_t, u_t, z_t)$ 
9     if  $\|\bar{m}_t - m_t\| > thr_1$  then
10       $rplCnt \leftarrow rplCnt + 1$ 
11      if  $rplCnt \% 5 == 0$  then
12       |  $iCnt \leftarrow 1$ 
13      else
14       |  $iCnt \leftarrow i$ 
15      break;
16   PublishVelRef ( $u_t$ )

```

Algorithm 1. BSP Algorithm.

In particular, the BSP approach demonstrated its effectiveness in fulfilling the goal even having to handle inaccurate and not precise measurements.

We performed both simulations and real-world tests, showing the practicality and effectiveness of the proposed approach.

(a) Starting position

(b) Final position

Fig. 3. REEM-C performing a walking simulation run within the Gazebo simulator environment.

5.5 Simulation and real-world experiments

Simulations were performed in terms of Scenario (1) and exploiting the Gazebo simulator Koenig and Howard (2004) in which a red sphere has been added into the bare environment, as shown in Figure 3. We performed several simulation runs, placing the red blob even 20 *m* far away from REEM-C and asking the robot to track and approach the object, stopping in front of it at a distance of 5 *m* and in such a way to have its image centered in REEM-C camera plane ($x - y$ plane). Figure 3 shows some moments of one of this walking simulation. Accordingly, the BSP task error, on-line computed by the system during the motion execution, is shown in Figure 6, relatively to a simulation run.

The real world experiments mixed Scenarios (1) and (2). Figure 4 depicts some moments of one of the walking experiments, on flat ground while tracking a moving target, that were performed at the IIT testing facility in Genoa within the HumaBeliefs project.

Due to the testing facility size, we were not able to ask the robot to stop at a distance of 5 *m* in front of the blob, but we asked REEM-C to center it in its camera image plane and to stop 1.5 *m* from it.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quantitative results of a typical simulation are plotted in Figure 5. Specifically, the evolution of both the red blob 3D position (w.r.t. REEM-C) estimated by the vision algorithm and REEM-C x - y position are shown. Note that REEM-C walks for about 14 *m* and 1 *m* along the x and y axes, respectively. Accordingly, the task is accomplished when the robot is in front of the red blob, at a distance of about 5 *m*, as shown by the estimated blob position in Figure 5(a); note that the blob estimation on the z axis (vertical) is affected by the robot head motion, induced by the walking itself.

Fig. 4. REEM-C performing a walking run in real-world experiments.

(a) Red blob 3D position

(b) REEM-C position on x - y axes

Fig. 5. Time evolution of the main variables during the walking task simulation

Fig. 6. BSP task error evolution during a walking simulation.

Figure 6 reports the time evolution of the BSP task error in a typical walking simulation. The plot is very similar to Figure 5(a), since the task error is strictly related to the residual distance between the blob and the robot. The task is considered completed when the error norm (i.e. the norm of the difference vector between the blob current and final desired position w.r.t. the robot camera) is below a predefined threshold, namely 0.7 m , meaning, for an initial task error norm of about 14 m , a requirement to reduce the error below 5%.

Concerning real-world experiments, we asked REEM-C to keep a distance from the blob of 1.5 m and allowed the final error norm to be below 0.2 m . The obtained performance in terms of robot motion and blob position estimation is shown in Figure 7. Peaks visible on the x -axis of Figure 7(a) correspond to moments in which the red target was moved around the facility and its position w.r.t. the robot camera abruptly changed. Note that whenever the blob is moved, the estimation of its position is highly noisy; this is due to different effects, among which temporary partial occlusions, motion blur, bad segmentation in the first frames after the blob position changed. However, due to the good convergence property of the BSP algorithm, the noise rapidly decreases, and the tracking could successfully be accomplished. In order to complete the assigned task, the robot is also capable of walking backwards whenever the blob was too close to it, as highlighted by the top plot of Figure 7(b). A video reporting both a simulation and a real-world test can be found here: https://shanghai-lectures.github.io/slides/IFAC_WC_2023__HumaBeliefs_multimedia.avi

It is important to notice that the results discussed here can be, by getting access to the Eurobench@Iit testing facilities, replicated to achieve the desired level of statistical significance and the reproducible platform will at least in principle allow to build on and improve our work.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The BSP has proven very robust and effective in managing uncertainties and unexpected situations in many different experimental settings. Our primary objective in this work was to check to what extent BSP could be used on a complex mechatronic platform such as a humanoid robot. The tests on REEM-C as a tool to implement what is known to be a plausible planning motion strategy in humans in

(a) Red blob 3D position

(b) REEM-C position on x-y axes

Fig. 7. Time evolution of the main variables during the walking task real-world experiment

conjunction with PAL Walking controllers has been very successful in the tasks of following a colored spot and keeping a predefined distance from it. However, in simulation, performance on slopes has been unsatisfactory. To this end, we will exploit PAL Robotics Whole-Body Controller (WBC) to achieve better performance on slopes; this, in turn, requires the computation of a Zero Moment Point (ZMP) solution for the contact points between ground and robot feet, as well as a suitable strategy for humanoid stabilization during walking. This has led our team to start to develop a tailor-made system, exploiting PAL WBC instead of their walking controller, modeling the biped walking dynamics with a Linear Inverted Pendulum Model (LIPM) solution and introducing an innovative BSP-based stabilizer (BSP-S). At the conclusion of the project, this novel dedicated WBC + LIPM system has been developed and tested with success in the real world in the case of standing on a single foot and in simulation in the case of walking on a flat surface. Future work will compare robustness and adaptivity of the BSP-S stabilizer against approaches based on MPC and other more conventional stabilizers.

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